

Laying the FOUNDATION

Early cartoonist

F. M. HOWARTH developed some of the idioms that later cartoonists relied on.

IAN GORDON explores the role Howarth played in the comic strip's formative period

The question “When did the comic strip start?” is a hoary one that every comics historian confronts. Complicating the answer to that question is defining precisely what a comic strip is. Some historians—including me—date comic strips from the debut of the Yellow Kid because of the widespread insistence that a continuing character is key to the American comic strip. If the Yellow Kid was the first comic strip, then, it gave rise to other features of the comic strip, such as the use of word balloons and sequential panels. Such definitions might suggest that comic strips are peculiarly American, but I maintain that comic strips were a feature of economic and social conditions in the United States at the end of the nineteenth century; the strip also developed elsewhere under similar conditions.

Tracing the comic strip’s lineage to the Yellow Kid has its advantages, but of course sequential panels and word balloons

predate the Yellow Kid. Similarly, sustained efforts at creating comic art featuring characters existed long before the Yellow Kid. The work of Switzerland’s Rodolphe Töpffer (1799–1846) and the German Wilhelm Busch (1832–1908) are the most frequently cited antecedents of much American comic art. The collective influence of Busch and, particularly, Töpffer was more considerable than has been acknowledged in most works on comics.

It would be far too simplistic to say that Busch and Töpffer influenced American cartoonists and resulted in the creation of the comic strip; many other artists inspired American cartoonists. Likewise, the transatlantic influence in illustration traveled in both directions between Europe and the United States. Indeed, in the late nineteenth century an earlier form of a global economy took shape, and one of its elements was an international popular culture of which comic art was but one aspect.

In researching American comic strips, I sought out the wellspring. I surveyed the illustrated humor journals—*Puck*, *Life* and *Judge*—from 1887 to 1900 and another journal, *Truth*, from 1893 to 1896. I began to realize that there was no single source—no smoking gun—that invariably linked European comic art to American comic strips. What I did find, however, was a number of artists whose work broached the comic-strip format without ever developing that form. Of these artists, Franklin Morris (F. M.) Howarth stood out from the pack.

Howarth worked as a bank clerk in Philadelphia in the 1880s while freelancing cartoons for numerous magazines, including *Judge* and *Life*. Eventually, Howarth moved to New York, probably around the mid-1890s, around the time he joined *Puck* as a full-time artist. In making this move, Howarth joined the company of other illustrators and newspaper artists such as John Sloan, the Glackens brothers—Louis and William—and George Luks.

Magazines such as *Puck*, *Life* and *Judge* acquainted readers with a new urban political and leisure culture, and by employing artists such as Howarth they introduced readers to a developing art form. Like Busch and Töpffer, Howarth narrowed the distance between the textual and the visual to create a hybridized comic art form that increased the emphasis on character and narrative by embedding them within the image itself.

Howarth was one of a number of American comic artists who attempted to yoke narrative humor with graphic illustration and was the most important of these magazine artists, for he did the most to develop humorous illustrated narratives. Howarth joined *Puck* as a full-time artist during the magazine's reign as the preeminent forum for illustrated humor. Unlike the other artists on the *Puck* staff, however, Howarth was not required to draw editorial cartoons. Given the trajectory of Howarth's career and of American illustrated humor, this was an important division of labor. It marked the point where artists and editors separated

Life, January 5, 1888

comic-strip art from political commentary. Howarth was one of the first major American comic artists to concentrate on social, or nonpolitical, humor. His work in *Puck* consisted mainly of sequential narratives, occasionally with text underneath, a format borrowed directly from Busch. Howarth's innovation was to block out his work in panels.

Howarth was the leading American proponent of multipaneled comic stories. This feature of Howarth's work was important in the development of comic art as a commodity, because it formed the basis for the creation of comic-strip characters. Narrative sequences were crucial to the development of comic-strip characters because the humor in these illustrations derived from a dynamic social setting in which elapsed time played a role. In these sequences, rather than using the figures as illustrations for gags printed beneath the panel, artists created the humor around the figures. Artists such as Howarth gave these figures characteristics attributed to city dwellers and created various types of comic-art figures.

Busch's influence can clearly be seen in many of Howarth's strips. For instance, both "The Wicked Grandsons" (*Life*, October 1, 1891) and "The Revenge of the Persecuted Baker" (*Judge*, July 11, 1891) owe much to Busch. The latter, in which two naughty boys steal pastries from an overladen baker who eventually exacts his revenge by lacing his goods with coal oil, directly reworks Busch's theme in *Max und Moritz*. Howarth's style, however, was more explicit than Busch's and conveyed the story without recourse to an exterior explanatory text. Although many of his strips were not blocked out with panels, Howarth established a rudimentary frame by changing the

position of figures. The narrative shifts in both strips also framed the action. In an earlier strip, "The Wicked Boys and the Humane Old Man" (*Life*, June 13, 1889), Howarth used the same rudimentary framing device and the depth and perspective of the panel to tell a sequential story.

Howarth also borrowed and developed techniques aimed at

expanding possibilities for character development. He experimented with graphic methods that captured feelings and emotions such as pain and anxiety.

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The last sequence of "The Revenge of the Persecuted Baker" shows the two boys in pain, depicted through contorted facial features, hands clenched to stomachs and

Life, March 21, 1889

A SMART BOY AND HIS GRAND-PAPA.

NOGAN'S ALLEY No. 9

aggerated sweat beads or tears pouring
own the boys' faces. Howarth used this
echnique in his earlier "The Unexpected"
Life, April 23, 1891), in which an Asian

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prisoner exudes large beads of sweat as he
awaits beheading.
Afterward, exaggerated sweat beads
became a standard means of displaying

THE WICKED BOYS AND THE HUMANE OLD MAN;
Or, VIRTUE REWARDED.

Life, June 13, 1889

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anxiety in American comic strips, and credit for this shorthand belongs to Howarth.

Howarth, along with numerous other artists, adopted one of Töpffer's techniques: the use of lines to depict motion. Motion lines are apparent in a number of Howarth strips, such as "The Country Bumpkin" (*Life*, January 5, 1888) and "The Unexpected." Clouds of dust, which indicate very quick motion, are an outgrowth of the development of motion lines, and Howarth used this technique in "A Wild Success" (*Life*, February 27, 1890).

A WILD SUCCESS.

Life, February 27, 1890

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As I studied Howarth's work from the late 1880s and early 1890s, I began to wonder why he had not become a successful comic-strip artist, one whose work appears in the standard works on the early

history of the form. Author Roy McCardle included Howarth in his June 1905 article on comic strips that was published in *Everybody's Magazine* ("Opper, Outcault and Company: The Comic Supplement and the Men Who Make It"), but Coulton Waugh's 1947 book *The Comics* dismissed the work of Howarth (whom he misnamed H. M. Howarth) as not in the great tradition. Why Howarth never became a great comic-strip artist was puzzling, because Howarth's use of narrative form and comic art technique allowed him to create new possibilities for comic characters. Rather than illustrate one or two line gags straight out of vaudeville, Howarth presented unfolding stories through a series of panels. But like vaudeville, these illustrations worked familiar narrative genres where the joke lay in the novel solution to a stock situation. Howarth's work made fun of professional photographers and spoiled babies, highlighted the pettiness of fashion and social class and depicted the numerous frustrations faced by suitors. For instance, in "Love Will Find the Way" (*Puck*, February 17, 1892), Howarth showed a young couple's triumph over a watchful father, while other strips showed suitors' efforts frustrated by vigilant fathers, jealous rivals and even uncooperative elephants. These figures and others, such as the overbearing mother-in-law, emerged as stock types, so much so that on occasions Howarth created his humor by overturning common

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expectations. For instance, he drew a strip where a suitor encountered an uncooperative father who secretly longed to marry off his daughter (*Puck*, March 23, 1892) and another in which a man's mother-in-law proved to be a godsend (*Puck*, January 4, 1893).

The most important of these pictorial representations of

his claim. By the late 1890s, his work in *Puck* had lost much of its earlier freshness. In many ways, his *Puck* work took a

social types in the development of American comic strips was the naughty boy originally borrowed from Busch's *Max und Moritz*. The first comic-strip character, the Yellow Kid, was developed from the naughty-boy type. Howarth was not the first American artist who borrowed Busch's naughty boys for his comic strips. The leading illustrator of the day, Frank Bellew, and his son, Chip, contributed several such strips to *Life* before Howarth. Chip's "How Katrina's Valentine Reached Her After All" (*Life*, February 15, 1894), laid out in eight text-free panels, demonstrates his style and ability. But neither Frank, who died in 1888, nor Chip, who died at 32 in 1894, developed work in the comics strip idiom on the scale of Howarth. Howarth's "The Revenge of the Persecuted Baker" occupied the whole back page of *Judge* and was in color. When he joined *Puck*, the full-page comic strip—combining rhyming text with images blocked out in panels—became his stock in trade. Howarth also regularly drew pieces focused on two naughty boys. In addition to "The Revenge of the Persecuted Baker," Howarth featured two boys in strips published in *Life* on October 1, 1891, and in *Puck* on May 10, 1893, August 19, 1896, and January 13, 1897. Moreover,

Judge

THE REVENGE OF THE PERSECUTED BAKER.

Judge, July 11, 1891

ALGERNON (*calling. Wild with rage.*) —
Gosh-blame this cursèd espionage—

(*Rising.*) I've struck on just the thing!
(*Aloud.*) Miss Mary, won't you sing?

(*Aside to MARY.*) Are you on?
MARY (*aside.*) — Yumps, Algernon.

(*Aloud.*) Sing, too; I guess you know 'm.
BOTH. — "Maggie Murphy's Ho-o-ome!"

ALGERNON. — Splendid! Now with me.
BOTH. — "Down . . . McGinty . . . bottom . . . sea!!"

MARY (*aside.*) — Now, let her go!
BOTH. — "She's my Annie, I'm her Joe!!!"

ALGERNON. — Whoop! That hit him bad.
BOTH. — "COMRADES!! COMRADES!!!"

Puck, February 17, 1892

(*Exit DAD.*)

ALGERNON. — Mary!
MARY. — Ally!
(*Embrace. Quick Curtain. Short Finale.*)

LOVE WILL FIND THE WAY.

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step back, including as it did explanatory text below the panels. This technique may have offered Howarth greater narrative possibilities, but to my mind it weakened the story he told in the panels. For instance, Howarth's "Look Before You Leap" (*Judge*, November 7, 1891), which has no text associated with its five panels, is a better piece than his seven-panel "One On the Dog" (*Puck*, September 30, 1896), which is accompanied by text. Part of the appeal of the former over the latter rests with the subject matter. "Look Before You Leap" features a man triumphing over an aggressive dog, whereas "One On the Dog" shows two burglars mistreating a dog. But, for me, the absence of text under the panels makes "Look Before You Leap" the superior piece of work because it trusts the reader's ability to follow the action without the signposts of text.

The central technical problem that Howarth didn't solve was figuring out a method of giving comics characters a voice, which allowed creators to imbue new depth in them. This problem went unsolved until late 1900 or early 1901 when artists such as Frederick B. Opper, in the *New York Journal*, began to use word balloons in strips on a regular basis. This development allowed for the greater development of comic-strip characters, which quickly became the backbone of the American comic strip.

In 1903 Howarth joined the Hearst stable, for which he drew *Lulu and Leander* in the familiar style of his *Puck* back-pagers. He never chose to employ word balloons on a regular basis, and compared to other strips *Lulu* was old-fashioned and the humor forced. This strip lasted but four years before Hearst canceled it in 1907. Howarth died in 1908. In the space of approximately ten years Howarth went from being an innovative force in comic art to a figure that the fast-developing form had passed by. Whether this was due to some creative blind spot in Howarth, a battle with the bottle to which many cartoonists succumbed or the rapid pace of development in comic art is open to conjecture. What is certain is that Howarth occupied an important early niche in the comic strip's formative period, and his work provides insights into once-innovative aspects of the comic strip that are commonplace today. ■

THE WICKED GRANDSONS.

Life, October 1, 1891